

Reliability Enhancement for V2V Communications: via AF Relay versus via Passive RIS

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Abstract—In advanced vehicular networks, Roadside Unit (RSU)-based amplify-and-forward (AF) relay and passive Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS) are two potential helpers to enhance the vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) communications when the direct link experiences poor quality. This paper presents a comprehensive comparison of the two enhancement modes from the outage performance perspective. In the presence of both direct link and enhanced link, the analytical expressions of the outage probability (OP) for the V2V communication under the two enhancement modes are derived respectively. Moreover, considering the co-channel interference caused by relay/RIS, the OP of the neighbouring vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communication is also derived. Additional analysis compares the diversity order and the strength of interference created by the V2V communication under the two enhancement modes. Further discussions are presented on the effect of the channel estimation error and phase quantization error under the RIS mode. Finally, the pros and cons of the two enhancement modes

are demonstrated by both the analytical and numerical results.

Index Terms—Reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS), vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V), relay, outage probability (OP), diversity order.

I. INTRODUCTION

To meet the global demand for a smarter and safer transportation system, vehicle-to-everything (V2X) is deemed as one of the key technologies [1]. Vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) communication, which can enable drivers to directly exchange local traffic condition and driving policies, is a significant part of V2X. With respect to the other communication types, V2V communication requires ultra-high reliability due to its strong influence on the security of everything around us. According to 3GPP TR22.886, the outage probability (OP) of the V2V communication should not exceed 10^{-4} for vehicle platooning and 10^{-5} for advanced driving in order to maintain the road safety [2]. Such stringent requirements, nevertheless, are confronted with great challenges in actual environments. One is that the pre-allocated carrier frequency of V2X is 5.9 GHz, which would suffer from extreme path loss when faced with long communication distances [3]. The other is that vehicles have no tall antennas, and thus, the V2V communication is easy to be blocked due to the shadowing of the other vehicles or roadside buildings [4].

For enhancing the reliability of V2V communications, the relay mode is a potential solution. If the receiver is far apart from the transmitter or is blocked by a shelter, a relay node can be employed to assist the transmission. In the transportation scenarios, what kind of device can serve as relay nodes? One option is another vehicle located between the transmitter and the receiver [5]. However, this mode has a fatal flaw that the relay vehicle always has unstable travelling speeds, thereby degrading the robustness of the relay links [6]. In view of this, roadside unit (RSU), a kind of active device to support vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communications, seems to be a better candidate. RSUs are always equipped with tall antennas to guarantee a wide signal coverage for vehicles, which offers countermeasure to shadow fading. Additionally, in the intended intelligent transportation system (ITS), RSUs will be densely deployed along the roadside, so that the relay of V2V communications can be seamless.

On the other hand, reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS), a surface comprised by plenty of passive electromagnetic materials, is emerging as a novel technology in communi-

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cation systems. By managing the reflection phase of each electromagnetic element, RIS can reflect the incoming signal to the receiver with a desired direction [7]. Hence, the RIS is another potential helper for enhancing the reliability of V2V communications. Actually, this idea is with great promise since the buildings or isolation barriers of roads are perfect carriers of RISs. If RISs are deployed at a right height, the shadow fading can also be mitigated.

As a matter of fact, there are distinct differences between the relay mode and the RIS mode [8]. (a) Relay is an active mode that can amplify-and-forward (AF) (or decode-and-forward) the signals, while RIS is a passive mode that only reflects the signals with a reflection coefficient smaller than 1. (b) Under the relay mode, the overall noise power at the receiver will be strengthened due to the amplification of the signal plus noise. Thanks to the passive structure without the need of active components, RISs do not introduce additional thermal noise to the receiver. (c) Large-scale array antennas can hardly be available at the relay due to the dramatic cost and space demands. On the contrary, the smaller antenna spacing and lower cost allow RISs to deploy massive elements in a given aperture, thereby achieving high diversity gains.

A few prior works have compared the outage performance of the two enhancement modes in low-mobility communication scenarios [9], [10]. They are, however, not applicable to V2V communications, which is exactly what motivates our work. (a) In these works, the direct link was assumed to be completely inexistent. Despite the serious shadow fading, short-distance V2V communications always have direct links. (b) They did not consider the interference created by the enhanced links. Actually, transmission interference is non-negligible in vehicular networks since the safety of the other vehicles may get affected. (c) They all assumed optimal phase shift for RISs. This assumption is overly idealistic in V2V communications since the fast time-varying channels and Doppler effect would result in obstinate phase noise.

In this paper, we present a vehicular system in the freeway environment where both RSUs and RISs are available for the V2V enhancement. The outage performance of the system under the two enhancement modes is systematically analyzed. The main contributions are summarized as follows.

- For the V2V communication with Rayleigh fading model, the closed-form expression of OP and the diversity order under the two enhancement modes are derived, respectively. Both the enhanced link and the direct link are taken into account, which greatly complicates the derivations.
- The co-channel interference from the enhanced V2V link to the neighbouring V2I communication is also considered, where the closed-form expression of OP for the V2I communication is derived. Additionally, the strength of interference created by the two modes are compared.
- Under the RIS mode with both channel estimation error and phase quantization error, the OP of the V2V communication is derived. The final expression of OP does not contain hypergeometric functions, which can offer insights as to what parameters determine the results.

- The correctness of our analysis is verified by extensive numerical simulations. Based on the analytical results as well as the numerical results, the pros and cons of the two enhancement modes are demonstrated.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews the related work. Section III describes the system model. Section IV derives the OP for the V2V communication and V2I communication under the relay mode. Section V derives the OP for the V2V communication and V2I communication under the RIS mode. Section VI compares the diversity order and the strength of interference achieved by the V2V communication under the two modes. Section VII analyzes the effect of phase noise on the outage performance of the V2V communication under the RIS mode. Section VIII shows the analytical results and numerical results. Finally, Section IX concludes this paper.

Notations: $\mathbb{E}[\cdot]$ and $\text{Var}[\cdot]$ denote the expectation and variance of a random variable, respectively. $|\cdot|$ represents the absolute value of a scalar. $\exp(\cdot)$ and $e^{(\cdot)}$ both represent the exponential function. $o(\cdot)$ denotes the higher-order infinitesimal of a variable. $A \bmod B$ stands for the remainder of $\frac{A}{B}$. $\Re\{\cdot\}$ and $\Im\{\cdot\}$ are the real part and the imaginary part of a complex number, respectively. $\Pr\{\cdot\}$ refers to the probability operator. $\Phi(\cdot)$ is the error function. $K_v(\cdot)$ is the v th-order Modified Bessel function of the second kind.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Reliability Analysis for V2V

Some researches have contributed to the reliability analysis of V2V communications [11]–[14]. In [11], the analytical expressions for the success probabilities of V2V communication was derived on orthogonal street systems involving intersections with Poisson distributed vehicles on each street. In [12], Keyhole fading effect was considered for dense V2V communication systems, and the outage probabilities were derived in closed form for different hybrid automatic repeat request (HARQ) assisted schemes. By utilizing Network Simulator 3, [13] performed experimental analysis of safety application reliability against beacon rates and vehicle densities for V2V communications, and concluded that there is a unique beacon rate that maximizes the safety performance. Authors of [14] provided an accurate statistical description of the V2V propagation and reported that the V2V communication is hard to achieve satisfactory outage performance if the direct link experiences poor quality.

B. Reliability Enhancement for V2V

To improve the reliability of V2V communications, a number of techniques have been proposed from different perspectives [15]–[17]. In [15], a resource size control (RSC) method, which adapts the resource size according to the macroscopic network parameters such as vehicle density, communication range, and message size, was proposed for improving link reliability of V2V communications. In [16], a distributed network coding-based medium access control protocol (NC-MAC), which combines the preamble-based feedback mechanism,

retransmissions, and network coding together, was proposed to enhance the reliability of V2V beacon broadcasting. Authors of [17] proposed a scheduling method with successive interference cancellation (SIC) for V2V networks, which can increase the number of decoded packets, and improve the robustness for the fading by setting the margin to slot allocation.

Transmission with relay is another way to enhance the reliability of V2V communications, which is tailored to the case that the direct link is of poor quality. Relay-aided V2V communications can be realized in different manners or for different goals [18]–[20]. In [18], RSU was used to serve as the decode-and-forward (DF) relay for a secondary V2V pair in the cognitive radio vehicular network with considering an eavesdropper vehicle. In [19], the optimal channel state information and noise assisted variable-gain (CSIN-VG) sub-scheme, the blind fixed-gain (B-FG) sub-scheme, and the semi-blind fixed-gain (SB-FG) sub-scheme were adopted and compared in V2V communications under the AF-based RSU relay mode. Furthermore, both RSUs and vehicles were employed in [20] to decode and forward essential information for V2V communications in platooning systems, and simulations demonstrated the benefit of the proposed relaying scheme.

C. Application of RIS in various types of networks

RIS can adjust the reflected signal to a specific direction, and therefore, it has been widely used to enhance desired signals or mitigate interference in various types of networks [21]–[25]. In [21] and [22], RIS was used to assist device-to-device (D2D) communications under Nakagami- m fading and circularly symmetric complex Gaussian (CSCG) fading channels, respectively. In [23], non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) cellular network employed RIS to enhance the desired signals of cell-edge users. In the multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) cognitive radio system given by [24], RIS was used to assist the data transmission of secondary users by optimizing the phase shifts. Moreover, authors of [25] proposed an RIS-aided cellular network, and studied the problem of power control at the base station (BS) for physical-layer broadcasting under quality of service constraints.

There also has been some researches considering the deployment of RISs to assist vehicular communications [26]–[28]. In [26], the RIS-assisted V2V communication system under multi-path interference was proposed, and the precise approximation for RIS-assisted V2V communication under Nakagami- m channels was derived in detail. Besides, authors of [27] proposed the cooperation of RIS and vehicles as relays to enable the scheduling of non-line-of-sight (NLOS) V2V requests in millimeter wave (mmWave) vehicular networks, so that as many V2V requests as possible can be fulfilled. In [28], a promising RIS-assisted V2I network model in a highway environment was proposed, and the downlink outage probability under Rayleigh fading channels was derived considering the inter-cell interference.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a vehicular network in the freeway environment where RSUs are uniformly deployed along the roadside to facilitate V2I communications. Also, RSUs can serve as relays of V2V communications when the direct V2V link suffers from poor quality due to long distance or serious shadow fading. Meanwhile, RISs are equipped on demand at the isolation barrier of the freeway. Without loss of generality, we focus on a possible segmental scenario within this network shown as Fig. 1 [29]. u_1 and u_2 are two neighbouring RSUs, and r is a passive RIS exactly under u_2 with N ($N \gg 1$) reflecting elements. u_2 contains a micro-controller that is connected to r , such that the reflection configuration of r is controlled by the micro-controller. u_1 has downlink V2I services tailored to vehicle v_1 . Vehicle v_2 and v_3 are paired V2V nodes with v_2 being the transmitter and v_3 being the receiver. The V2V communication undergoes severe shadow fading caused by another vehicle between v_2 and v_3 . In this regard, either u_2 or r can serve as the helper to enhance the V2V communication, which can be termed as relay mode and RIS mode, respectively. We will investigate the impact of different enhancement modes on the outage performance of the V2V communication and its neighbouring V2I communication.

For any two nodes x and y (RSU/RIS/vehicle), let $G_{xy}(t) = L_{xy}(t)h_{xy}(t)\exp(j[\varphi_{xy}(t) + \vartheta_{xy}(t)])$ be the channel gain of link $x \rightarrow y$ at time t , where $h_{xy}(t)$ denotes the small-scale channel coefficient following independent identically distributed (i.i.d.) Rayleigh fading model with expectation $\mathbb{E}[h_{xy}(t)] = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}}\sigma$ and variance $\text{Var}[h_{xy}(t)] = \frac{4-\pi}{2}\sigma^2$; $\varphi_{xy}(t)$ is the corresponding channel phase uniformly distributed between $[0, 2\pi)$. The probability density function (PDF) of $h_{xy}(t)$ can be identically expressed as

$$f_{h_{xy}(t)}(s) = \frac{s}{\sigma^2} \exp\left(-\frac{s^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad s > 0, \quad (1)$$

and therefore $|G_{xy}(t)|$ follows the PDF of

$$f_{|G_{xy}(t)|}(s) = \frac{s}{L_{xy}^2(t)\sigma^2} \exp\left(-\frac{s^2}{2L_{xy}^2(t)\sigma^2}\right), \quad s > 0. \quad (2)$$

Furthermore, $L_{xy}(t)$ denotes the large-scale channel coefficient of link $x \rightarrow y$ with considering both the propagation distance and the shadow fading; $\vartheta_{xy}(t) = 2\pi\frac{f_{xy}(t)}{f_c}$ is the phase shift created by Doppler effect, where $f_{xy}(t)$ stands for the Doppler shift and f_c is the carrier frequency.

Let s_x denote the transmitting symbol of x such that $\mathbb{E}[|s_x|^2] = 1$, and P_x denote the transmitting power of x . The additive circular symmetric complex Gaussian noise at y can be denoted as $n_y(t)$, which has zero-mean and variance of σ_0^2 [30]. For the sake of simplicity, we omit the argument t for all the time-varying variables hereafter. It is assumed that all the RSUs and vehicles are equipped with only one antenna and work at the same frequency. With regard to the V2V communication under the relay mode, both of direct link $v_2 \rightarrow v_3$ and cascaded link $v_2 \rightarrow u_2 \rightarrow v_3$ provide desired

Fig. 1. System model.

signals. Then the received signal at v_3 can be written as

$$Y_3^u = G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda \left(G_{v_2 u_2} \sqrt{P_{v_2}} s_{v_2} + n_{u_2} \right) + G_{v_2 v_3} \sqrt{P_{v_2}} s_{v_2} + n_{v_3} \quad (3)$$

where λ represents the voltage amplification gain of u_2 .

Despite the enhancement of the V2V communication, we note that u_2 may become an interferer of v_1 . Therefore, the impact of the V2V relaying on the V2I communication is also taken into account. Specifically, link $u_1 \rightarrow v_1$ provides desired signals, while link $v_2 \rightarrow u_2 \rightarrow v_1$ is the interference. Then the received signal at v_1 under the relay mode of the V2V communication can be written as

$$Y_1^u = G_{u_2 v_1} \lambda \left(G_{v_2 u_2} \sqrt{P_{v_2}} s_{v_2} + n_{u_2} \right) + G_{u_1 v_1} \sqrt{P_{u_1}} s_{u_1} + n_{v_1}. \quad (4)$$

With regard to the V2V communication under the RIS mode, the transmission model is slightly different from that under the relay mode. Specifically, the signal received by v_3 under the RIS mode can be expressed as

$$Y_3^r = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} G_{r_n v_3} \eta e^{j\phi_{r_n}} G_{v_2 r_n} \sqrt{P_{v_2}} s_{v_2} + G_{v_2 v_3} \sqrt{P_{v_2}} s_{v_2} + n_{v_3} \quad (5)$$

where $\mathcal{N} = \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ denotes the indexes of all the reflecting elements in r , and r_n is the n -th element; η represents the reflection coefficient of all the elements and ϕ_{r_n} stands for the phase shift induced by r_n .

Similarly, we can express the received signal at v_1 under the RIS mode of the V2V communication as

$$Y_1^r = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} G_{r_n v_1} \eta e^{j\phi_{r_n}} G_{v_2 r_n} \sqrt{P_{v_2}} s_{v_2} + G_{u_1 v_1} \sqrt{P_{u_1}} s_{u_1} + n_{v_1}. \quad (6)$$

IV. OUTAGE PERFORMANCE UNDER RELAY MODE

This section mainly considers the relay enhancement mode for the V2V communication. We first derive and analyze the OP of the V2V communication based on (3), and then derive and analyze the OP of the V2I communication based on (4).

A. Outage Probability of V2V Communication

The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at v_3 under the RSU relay mode can be expressed as $\gamma_3^u = \frac{S_3^u}{I_3^u}$, where S_3^u is the desired

signal power and I_3^u is the noise power. From (3), S_3^u and I_3^u are given by

$$\begin{cases} S_3^u = |G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda G_{v_2 u_2} + G_{v_2 v_3}|^2 P_{v_2} \\ I_3^u = (|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda|^2 + 1) \sigma_0^2. \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

We denote the SNR at the transmitter as $\gamma_0 = \frac{P_{v_2}}{\sigma_0^2}$, and then there is $\gamma_3^u = X_3^u \gamma_0$ with $X_3^u = \frac{|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda G_{v_2 u_2} + G_{v_2 v_3}|^2}{|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda|^2 + 1}$. In the best case where ideal channel estimation is available at the receiver, the phase difference between the direct link and the enhanced link can be compensated, and then X_3^u can be rewritten as

$$X_3^u = \frac{(|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda G_{v_2 u_2}| + |G_{v_2 v_3}|)^2}{|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda|^2 + 1}. \quad (8)$$

Given a certain threshold γ_{th} , the OP at v_3 is given by (9) (shown on top of the next page), which is an intractable integral that has no closed-form expression. In view of this, we resort to the approximation of X_3^u in two limited cases, to gain insight into p_3^u with closed-form expressions.

Case 1: In the low λ regime, the overall noise will be dominated by the thermal noise introduced at the receiver. Given $|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda|^2 \ll 1$, then there is

$$X_3^u \approx (|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda G_{v_2 u_2}| + |G_{v_2 v_3}|)^2. \quad (10)$$

It is still hard to directly derive the OP for the approximate X_3^u with regular integration methods since it involves non-elementary functions [31]. However, we notice that the current form of X_3^u is the square of the sum of two independent random variables (RVs), i.e., $|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda G_{v_2 u_2}|$ and $|G_{v_2 v_3}|$. Gamma distribution is often used to approximate the distribution of some combinatorial variables due to its generality in tuning its PDFs with two parameters (shape parameter and scale parameter) [32]. Here we approximate the distribution of X_3^u by a Gamma distribution, and have the following proposition.

Proposition 1. *By using the Gamma approximation method, the PDF of X_3^u can be approximated by*

$$f_{X_3^u}(s) = \frac{s^{\alpha-1} \exp\left(-\frac{s}{\beta}\right)}{\Gamma(\alpha) \beta^\alpha} \quad (11)$$

with $\alpha = \frac{a^2}{b-a^2}$ and $\beta = \frac{b-a^2}{a} \frac{L_{v_2 v_3}^2}{c_0^2}$, where $a = 4\sigma^4 + \frac{\pi\sqrt{2\pi}}{2}\sigma^3 c_0 + 2\sigma^2 c_0^2$, $b = 8\sigma^4 c_0^4 + 3\pi\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma^5 c_0^3 + 48\sigma^6 c_0^2 + 9\pi\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma^7 c_0 + 64\sigma^8$, and $c_0 = \frac{L_{v_2 v_3}}{L_{u_2 v_3} \lambda L_{v_2 u_2}}$.

Proof: See Appendix A. ■

Corollary 1. *Under the relay mode, the approximate OP at v_3 is $p_3^u = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \gamma\left(\alpha, \frac{\gamma_{th}}{\beta \gamma_0}\right)$ in the low λ regime, where $\gamma(z, m) = \int_0^m \mu^{z-1} \exp(-\mu) d\mu$ is the incomplete gamma function, and p_3^u tends to $1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\gamma_{th}}{2\gamma_0 L_{v_2 v_3}^2 \sigma^2}\right)$ when $\lambda \rightarrow 0^+$.*

Proof: The calculation of p_3^u is straightforward from $p_3^u = \int_0^{\frac{\gamma_{th}}{\gamma_0}} f_{X_3^u}(s) ds$. When $\lambda \rightarrow 0^+$, there is $c_0 \rightarrow +\infty$. Then we can obtain $a = 2\sigma^2 c_0^2 + o(c_0^2)$, $a^2 = 4\sigma^4 c_0^4 + o(c_0^4)$ and

$$p_3^u = \Pr \left\{ X_3^u \leq \frac{\gamma_{\text{th}}}{\gamma_0} \right\} = \int_0^\infty \int_0^{\sqrt{\frac{\gamma_{\text{th}}}{\gamma_0} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\lambda^2 s^2}\right)}} \int_0^{\sqrt{\frac{\gamma_{\text{th}}}{\gamma_0} (1 + \lambda^2 s^2)} - \lambda s z} f_{|G_{v_2 v_3}|}(\mu) f_{|G_{v_2 u_2}|}(z) f_{|G_{u_2 v_3}|}(s) \, d\mu dz ds \quad (9)$$

$b = 8\sigma^4 c_0^4 + o(c_0^4)$. Thus, there are $\lim_{c_0 \rightarrow +\infty} \alpha = 1$ and $\lim_{c_0 \rightarrow +\infty} \beta = 2L_{v_2 v_3}^2 \sigma^2$. By substituting $\alpha = 1$ and $\beta = 2L_{v_2 v_3}^2 \sigma^2$ into the expression of p_3^u , we can obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow 0^+} p_3^u &= \int_0^{\frac{\gamma_{\text{th}}}{2\gamma_0 L_{v_2 v_3}^2 \sigma^2}} \exp(-\mu) \, d\mu \\ &= 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\gamma_{\text{th}}}{2\gamma_0 L_{v_2 v_3}^2 \sigma^2}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The proof is completed. \blacksquare

Remark 1. By performing the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, we find that the Kolmogorov-Smirnov distance (KSD) of cumulative distribution function (CDF) of X_3^u does not exceed 0.01 when $\lambda \leq 10^4$ (80 dB), which validates the good performance of the Gamma approximation. When λ tends to 0, the enhanced link can be ignored, and then there is $X_3^u \simeq |G_{v_2 v_3}|^2$, which can also result in (12). However, when it comes to the high λ regime, Proposition 1 becomes inapplicable since $|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda|^2 \ll 1$ no longer holds.

Case 2: In the high λ regime, the overall noise will be dominated by the noise introduced at the relay. Given $|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda|^2 \gg 1$, then there is

$$X_3^u \approx \left(|G_{v_2 u_2}| + \frac{|G_{v_2 v_3}|}{|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda|} \right)^2. \quad (13)$$

It is also hard to directly derive the OP for the approximate X_3^u with regular integration methods. Moreover, the Gamma approximation method also loses efficacy in this case due to the fact that the k -th moment ($k > 1$) of $\frac{|G_{v_2 v_3}|}{|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda|}$ does not exist¹. By observing that Rayleigh-based $|G_{v_2 u_2}|$ is much larger than $\frac{|G_{v_2 v_3}|}{|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda|}$ in the high λ regime, we attempt to approximate X_3^u with exponential distribution in a less rigorous manner. Different from the Gamma approximation, the exponential approximation only needs the first moment of $\frac{|G_{v_2 v_3}|}{|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda|}$, which guarantees the feasibility of our operation.

Proposition 2. *By using the exponential approximation method, the PDF of X_3^u can be approximated by $f_{X_3^u}(s) = c_1 \exp(-c_1 s)$ with $c_1 = \frac{\pi}{(c_0 \pi + \sqrt{2\pi} \sigma)^2 L_{v_2 v_3}^2}$.*

Proof: See Appendix B. \blacksquare

Corollary 2. *Under the relay mode, the approximate OP at v_3 is $p_3^u = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\gamma_{\text{th}}}{\gamma_0} c_1\right)$ in the high λ regime, and p_3^u tends to $1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\gamma_{\text{th}}}{2\gamma_0 L_{v_2 u_2}^2 \sigma^2}\right)$ when $\lambda \rightarrow +\infty$.*

Proof: The calculation of p_3^u is straightforward from $p_3^u = \int_0^{\frac{\gamma_{\text{th}}}{\gamma_0}} f_{X_3^u}(s) ds$. When $\lambda \rightarrow +\infty$, there is $c_0 \rightarrow 0^+$. Then we can obtain $\lim_{c_0 \rightarrow 0^+} c_1 = \frac{1}{2\sigma^2 L_{v_2 u_2}^2}$, and substituting it into

the expression of p_3^u , $\lim_{\lambda \rightarrow +\infty} p_3^u = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\gamma_{\text{th}}}{2\gamma_0 L_{v_2 u_2}^2 \sigma^2}\right)$ yields. The proof is completed. \blacksquare

Remark 2. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test also validates the good performance of the exponential approximation with the KSD of CDF of X_3^u smaller than 0.01 when $\lambda \geq 10^6$ (120 dB). When λ tends to infinity, the direct link can be ignored, and then there is $X_3^u \simeq \frac{|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda G_{v_2 u_2}|^2}{|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda|^2} = |G_{v_2 u_2}|^2$, which can also result in Corollary 2. From Proposition 2, p_3^u is a monotonically increasing function of λ , which indicates that improving λ is not a smart behavior in the high λ regime. It is because not only the desired signal but also the noise at u_2 is amplified by the relay. In the high λ regime, the strength of signal grows slower than the strength of noise. Therefore, in order to minimize the OP of the V2V communication under the relay mode, λ must be properly tuned.

B. Outage Probability of V2I Communication

The signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) at v_1 under the relay mode can be expressed as $\gamma_1^u = \frac{S_1^u}{I_1^u}$, where S_1^u is the desired signal power and I_1^u is the interference plus noise power. From (4), S_1^u and I_1^u are given by

$$\begin{cases} S_1^u = |G_{u_1 v_1}|^2 P_{u_1}, \\ I_1^u = |G_{u_2 v_1} \lambda|^2 (|G_{v_2 u_2}|^2 P_{v_2} + \sigma_0^2) + \sigma_0^2. \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Generally, $|G_{v_2 u_2}|^2 P_{v_2} \gg \sigma_0^2$ holds without severe shadowing in the link $v_2 \rightarrow u_2$. Hence, I_1^u can be approximately expressed as $I_1^u \approx |G_{u_2 v_1} \lambda|^2 |G_{v_2 u_2}|^2 P_{v_2} + \sigma_0^2$. Then we derive the closed-form expression of OP for the V2I communication as follows.

Proposition 3. *Under the relay mode of the V2V communication, the OP at v_1 is*

$$p_1^u = 1 - \frac{\sqrt{c_2}}{2c_3 \sqrt{\gamma_{\text{th}}}} \exp\left(\frac{c_2}{8c_3^2 \gamma_{\text{th}}} - \frac{\sigma_0^2 \gamma_{\text{th}}}{c_2}\right) W_{-\frac{1}{2}, 0}\left(\frac{c_2}{4c_3^2 \gamma_{\text{th}}}\right) \quad (15)$$

with $c_2 = 2\sigma^2 L_{u_1 v_1}^2 P_{u_1}$ and $c_3 = \lambda L_{u_2 v_1} L_{v_2 u_2} \sigma^2 \sqrt{P_{v_2}}$, where $W_{-\frac{1}{2}, 0}(\cdot)$ is the Whittaker function.

Proof: Given $\mathcal{H} = h_{u_2 v_1}^2 h_{v_2 u_2}^2$, then the PDF of \mathcal{H} can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} f_{\mathcal{H}}(z) &= \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{s} f_{h_{u_2 v_1}^2}(s) f_{h_{v_2 u_2}^2}\left(\frac{z}{s}\right) ds \\ &= \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{4\sigma^4} \frac{1}{s} \exp\left(-\frac{s}{2\sigma^2} - \frac{z}{2\sigma^2 s}\right) ds \\ &= \frac{1}{2\sigma^4} K_0\left(\frac{\sqrt{z}}{\sigma^2}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $f_{h_{xy}^2}(s) = \frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \exp\left(-\frac{s}{2\sigma^2}\right)$ according to (1). Thus, the PDF of I_1^u is

$$f_{I_1^u}(z) = \frac{1}{2c_3^2} K_0\left(\frac{\sqrt{z - \sigma_0^2}}{c_3}\right), \quad z > \sigma_0^2. \quad (17)$$

¹It can be proved following the way given by Appendix A.

On the other hand, the PDF of S_1^u is

$$f_{S_1^u}(s) = \frac{1}{c_2} \exp\left(-\frac{s}{c_2}\right). \quad (18)$$

Then the OP of the V2I communication can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} p_1^u &= \int_{\sigma_0^2}^{\infty} \int_0^{\gamma_{\text{th}} z} f_{S_1^u}(s) f_{I_1^u}(z) ds dz \\ &= \underbrace{\int_{\sigma_0^2}^{\infty} f_{I_1^u}(z) dz}_{p_{11}^u} - \underbrace{\int_{\sigma_0^2}^{\infty} f_{I_1^u}(z) \exp\left(-\frac{\gamma_{\text{th}} z}{c_2}\right) dz}_{p_{12}^u}. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

It is clear that $p_{11}^u = 1$, while p_{12}^u can be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} p_{12}^u &= \int_{\sigma_0^2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2c_3^2} K_0\left(\frac{\sqrt{z - \sigma_0^2}}{c_3}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{\gamma_{\text{th}} z}{c_2}\right) dz \\ &= \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{2c_3^2} K_0\left(\frac{\sqrt{z}}{c_3}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{\gamma_{\text{th}}(z + \sigma_0^2)}{c_2}\right) dz \\ &\stackrel{(d)}{=} \frac{\sqrt{c_2}}{2c_3 \sqrt{\gamma_{\text{th}}}} \exp\left(\frac{c_2}{8c_3^2 \gamma_{\text{th}}} - \frac{\sigma_0^2 \gamma_{\text{th}}}{c_2}\right) W_{-\frac{1}{2}, 0}\left(\frac{c_2}{4c_3^2 \gamma_{\text{th}}}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where equality (d) comes from the formula given by [31, Eq. (6.614-4)]. By substituting (20) into (19), the closed form of p_1^u can be obtained, and the proof is completed. ■

Corollary 3. *Under the relay mode of the V2V communication, the OP at v_1 tends to 1 when $\lambda \rightarrow +\infty$.*

Proof: It is clear that if $\lambda \rightarrow +\infty$, then there is $c_3 \rightarrow +\infty$, which results in

$$\begin{cases} \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{\sqrt{c_2}}{2c_3 \sqrt{\gamma_{\text{th}}}} = 0, \\ \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow +\infty} \exp\left(\frac{c_2}{8c_3^2 \gamma_{\text{th}}} - \frac{\sigma_0^2 \gamma_{\text{th}}}{c_2}\right) = \exp\left(-\frac{\sigma_0^2 \gamma_{\text{th}}}{c_2}\right), \\ \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow +\infty} W_{-\frac{1}{2}, 0}\left(\frac{c_2}{4c_3^2 \gamma_{\text{th}}}\right) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

Then we obtain $\lim_{\lambda \rightarrow +\infty} p_1^u = 1$. The proof is completed. ■

Remark 3. From Proposition 3, p_1^u is a monotonically increasing function of λ , which indicates that improving λ will create more serious interference to the V2I communication. When λ tends to infinity, there is $\gamma_1^u \simeq 0$, which can also result in Corollary 3. It is worth mentioning that this paper only considers a single antenna used for relaying. If multiple antennas are available, the V2V communication can be furtherly enhanced while the interference to the V2I communication can be mitigated by beamforming [8]. Multiple antennas, especially large-scale array antennas, however, require much heavier hardware cost (due to expensive Radio Frequency components) and power consumption (due to the active mode) than passive RIS. To this end, we only consider the single-antenna case for a fair comparison with the RIS mode.

V. OUTAGE PERFORMANCE UNDER RIS MODE

This section mainly considers the RIS enhancement mode for the V2V communication. We first derive and analyze the OP of the V2V communication based on (5), and then derive and analyze the OP of the V2I communication based on (6).

A. Outage Probability of V2V Communication

The SNR at v_3 under the RIS mode can be expressed as $\gamma_3^r = \frac{S_3^r}{I_3^r}$, where S_3^r is the desired signal power and $I_3^r = \sigma_0^2$ is the averaged noise power. From (5), γ_3^r is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_3^r &= \left| \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} G_{r_n v_3} \eta e^{j\phi_{r_n}} G_{v_2 r_n} + G_{v_2 v_3} \right|^2 \gamma_0 \\ &= \left| \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \mathcal{B}_n e^{j\psi_n} + \mathcal{A} e^{j(\varphi_{v_2 v_3} + \vartheta_{v_2 v_3})} \right|^2 \gamma_0 \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where $\mathcal{B}_n = \eta |G_{r_n v_3}| |G_{v_2 r_n}|$, $\mathcal{A} = |G_{v_2 v_3}|$, $\psi_n = \phi_{r_n} + (\varphi_{r_n v_3} + \vartheta_{r_n v_3}) + (\varphi_{v_2 r_n} + \vartheta_{v_2 r_n})$. ψ_n is the overall phase of the cascaded channel $v_2 \rightarrow r_n \rightarrow v_3$. The goal of the RIS is to adaptively adjust the phase shift of each element to enhance the desired signal. To give a theoretical analysis, imperfect phase shift of the RIS is not considered in this section. That is, the RIS is assumed to have ideal channel knowledge at any given moment, and the reflector phases of the RIS can be set precisely. Thus, to maximize the SNR, ψ_n has to satisfy $\psi_n = \varphi_{v_2 v_3} + \vartheta_{v_2 v_3}$. Then the optimal phase shift of r_n is

$$\phi_{r_n} = (\psi_{v_2 v_3} - \psi_{r_n v_3} - \psi_{v_2 r_n}) \bmod 2\pi, \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N} \quad (23)$$

where $\psi_{xy} = (\varphi_{xy} + \vartheta_{xy}) \bmod 2\pi$. With optimal ϕ_{r_n} , (22) can be simplified to

$$\gamma_3^r = \left(\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \mathcal{B}_n + \mathcal{A} \right)^2 \gamma_0. \quad (24)$$

Define $\mathcal{B} = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \mathcal{B}_n$, and then \mathcal{B} can be deemed as a combinatorial RV which is the summation of N independent RVs. According to central limit theorem (CLT), \mathcal{B} approximately follows Gaussian distribution when N is sufficiently large. Thus, the PDF of \mathcal{B} can be expressed as

$$f_{\mathcal{B}}(s) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_{\mathcal{B}}^2}} \exp\left[-\frac{(s - \mu_{\mathcal{B}})^2}{2\sigma_{\mathcal{B}}^2}\right] \quad (25)$$

with

$$\begin{cases} \mu_{\mathcal{B}} = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \frac{\pi}{2} \eta L_{r_n v_3} L_{v_2 r_n} \sigma^2 \\ \sigma_{\mathcal{B}}^2 = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \left(4 - \frac{\pi^2}{4}\right) \eta^2 L_{r_n v_3}^2 L_{v_2 r_n}^2 \sigma^4. \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

Then we have the following proposition.

Proposition 4. *Under the RIS mode with optimal phase shift, the approximate OP at v_3 is given by (27) (shown on top of the next page), where $\gamma_b = \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_{\text{th}}}{\gamma_0}}$, $c_4 = \sigma^2 L_{v_2 v_3}^2$, and $c_5 = \sqrt{\frac{c_4 + \sigma_{\mathcal{B}}^2}{c_4 \sigma_{\mathcal{B}}^2}}$.*

Proof: See Appendix C. ■

Corollary 4. *Under the RIS mode with optimal phase shift, the OP at v_3 tends to 0 when $N \rightarrow +\infty$.*

Proof: It can be assumed that all the enhanced links experience the identical large-scale fading due to the trivial

$$p_3^r = \frac{1}{2}\Phi\left(\frac{\gamma_b - \mu_B}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_B}\right) + \frac{1}{2}\Phi\left(\frac{\mu_B}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_B}\right) - \frac{1}{2\sigma_B c_5} \left[\Phi\left(\frac{c_4\mu_B + \gamma_b\sigma_B^2}{\sqrt{2}c_4\sigma_B^2 c_5}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{\gamma_b - \mu_B}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_B^2 c_5}\right) \right] \exp\left[-\frac{(\gamma_b - \mu_B)^2}{2\sigma_B^2 + 2c_4}\right] \quad (27)$$

size of the RIS panel relative to the communication distance [33], i.e., $L_{r_n v_3} \approx L_{rv_3}$ and $L_{v_2 r_n} \approx L_{v_2 r}$, $\forall n \in \mathcal{N}$. Therefore, (26) can be transformed into

$$\begin{cases} \mu_B \approx \frac{\pi}{2} N \eta L_{rv_3} L_{v_2 r} \sigma^2 \\ \sigma_B^2 \approx \left(4 - \frac{\pi^2}{4}\right) N \eta^2 L_{rv_3}^2 L_{v_2 r}^2 \sigma^4. \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

When $N \rightarrow +\infty$, we obtain $\mu_B \rightarrow +\infty$, $\sigma_B^2 \rightarrow +\infty$, and

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{\mu_B}{\sigma_B^2} = \frac{2\pi}{(16 - \pi^2) \eta L_{rv_3} L_{v_2 r} \sigma^2} = C. \quad (29)$$

Consequently, the following formulas can be obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{N \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{1}{2}\Phi\left(\frac{\gamma_b - \mu_B}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_B}\right) + \frac{1}{2}\Phi\left(\frac{\mu_B}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_B}\right) \\ = \frac{1}{2}\Phi\left(\frac{-\mu_B}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_B}\right) + \frac{1}{2}\Phi\left(\frac{\mu_B}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_B}\right) = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{N \rightarrow +\infty} \Phi\left(\frac{c_4\mu_B + \gamma_b\sigma_B^2}{\sqrt{2}c_4\sigma_B^2 c_5}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{\gamma_b - \mu_B}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_B^2 c_5}\right) \\ = \Phi\left(\frac{C}{\sqrt{2}c_5} + \frac{\gamma_b}{\sqrt{2}c_4 c_5}\right) + \Phi\left(-\frac{C}{\sqrt{2}c_5}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{N \rightarrow +\infty} \exp\left[-\frac{(\gamma_b - \mu_B)^2}{2\sigma_B^2 + 2c_4}\right] = \exp\left(-\frac{\mu_B^2}{2\sigma_B^2}\right) \\ = \exp\left(-\frac{\pi^2 N}{32 - 2\pi^2}\right) = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

Substituting (30), (31) and (32) into (27), $\lim_{N \rightarrow +\infty} p_3^r = 0$ yields. The proof is completed. ■

Remark 4. Obviously, the SNR at v_3 scales with N^2 if optimal phase shift can be achieved. By unlimitedly increasing the number of elements in the RIS, the OP of the V2V communication will approach 0. This is because there is negligible thermal noise attached in the passive reflecting elements under the RIS mode, which is totally different from the relay mode.

B. Outage Probability of V2I communication

The SINR at v_1 under the RIS mode can be expressed as $\gamma_1^r = \frac{S_1^r}{I_1^r}$, where S_1^r is the desired signal power and I_1^r is the interference plus noise power. From (6), I_1^r is given by

$$\begin{aligned} I_1^r &= \left| \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} G_{r_n v_1} \eta e^{j\phi_{r_n}} G_{v_2 r_n} \right|^2 P_{v_2} + \sigma_0^2 \\ &= \left| \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \mathcal{D}_n e^{j\theta_n} \right|^2 P_{v_2} + \sigma_0^2 \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

where $\mathcal{D}_n = \eta |G_{r_n v_1}| |G_{v_2 r_n}|$ and $\theta_n = (\phi_{r_n} + \psi_{r_n v_1} + \psi_{v_2 r_n}) \bmod 2\pi$. With regard to (33), we have the following two lemmas.

Lemma 1. θ_n is uniformly distributed between $[0, 2\pi)$.

Proof: See Appendix D. ■

Lemma 2. Given $N \gg 1$, then $\mathcal{D} = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \mathcal{D}_n e^{j\theta_n}$ approximately follows Zero Mean Complex Gaussian distribution, whose variance is $\sigma_{\mathcal{D}}^2 = 4\eta^2 \sigma^4 \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} L_{r_n v_1}^2 L_{v_2 r_n}^2$.

Proof: See Appendix E. ■

Based on Lemma 1 and Lemma 2, the following proposition can be obtained.

Proposition 5. Under the RIS mode of the V2V communication, the OP at v_1 is

$$p_1^r = 1 - \frac{c_2}{c_2 + \gamma_{\text{th}} \sigma_{\mathcal{D}}^2 P_{v_2}} \exp\left(-\frac{\gamma_{\text{th}} \sigma_0^2}{c_2}\right), \quad (34)$$

and p_1^r tends to 1 when $N \rightarrow +\infty$.

Proof: It is known that the modulus of a complex Gaussian variable follows Rayleigh distribution. Therefore, $|\mathcal{D}|^2$ will follow exponential distribution, the PDF of which is $f_{|\mathcal{D}|^2}(s) = \frac{1}{\sigma_{\mathcal{D}}^2} \exp\left(-\frac{s}{\sigma_{\mathcal{D}}^2}\right)$. Then the PDF of I_1^r is

$$f_{I_1^r}(i) = \frac{1}{\sigma_{\mathcal{D}}^2 P_{v_2}} \exp\left(-\frac{s - \sigma_0^2}{\sigma_{\mathcal{D}}^2 P_{v_2}}\right), \quad s > \sigma_0^2. \quad (35)$$

Meanwhile, the PDF of S_1^r is exactly the same as (18). Thus, the OP at v_1 is

$$\begin{aligned} p_1^r &= \int_{\sigma_0^2}^{\infty} f_{I_1^r}(z) \int_0^{\gamma_{\text{th}} z} \frac{1}{c_2} \exp\left(-\frac{s}{c_2}\right) ds dz \\ &= \int_{\sigma_0^2}^{\infty} f_{I_1^r}(z) \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{\gamma_{\text{th}} z}{c_2}\right)\right] dz \\ &= 1 - \frac{c_2}{c_2 + \gamma_{\text{th}} \sigma_{\mathcal{D}}^2 P_{v_2}} \exp\left(-\frac{\gamma_{\text{th}} \sigma_0^2}{c_2}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

It is clear that if $N \rightarrow +\infty$, then $\sigma_{\mathcal{D}}^2 \rightarrow +\infty$, which finally results in $\lim_{N \rightarrow +\infty} p_1^r = 1$. The proof is completed. ■

Remark 5. From Proposition 5, p_1^r is a monotonically increasing function of N , which indicates that increasing the number of elements in the RIS will create more serious interference to the V2I communication. In section VIII, however, we will demonstrate that the strength of interference created by the RIS is negligible w.r.t. that created by the relay when the two modes provide comparable enhancement to the V2V communication.

VI. DIVERSITY ORDER AND INTERFERENCE COMPARISON

In this section, we give some additional analysis to the performance of the two enhancement modes. Specifically, we derive the diversity order of the enhanced V2V communication, and compare the strength of interference suffered by the V2I communication under the two modes.

A. Diversity Order of V2V Communication

The diversity order provides useful information about how the OP decays in the high SNR regime. It is defined as the magnitude of the slope of OP against SNR in a log-log scale [34], i.e.,

$$d_v = - \lim_{\gamma \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{\log p_{\text{out}}(\gamma)}{\log \gamma} \quad (37)$$

where γ is the SNR at the transmitter and $p_{\text{out}}(\gamma)$ is the OP function of γ . With regard to our system, we present the following lemma.

Lemma 3. *Given three received SNR models respectively shown as $\gamma_a = h_{x_1 y_1}^2 \gamma$, $\gamma_b = h_{x_1 y_1}^2 h_{x_2 y_2}^2 \gamma$ and $\gamma_c = \frac{h_{x_1 y_1}^2}{h_{x_2 y_2}^2 + J} \gamma$, where $h_{x_1 y_1}$ and $h_{x_2 y_2}$ are two Rayleigh-based i.i.d. RVs with scale parameter σ and J is a non-negative constant, they can all achieve the diversity order of 1.*

Proof: See Appendix F. ■

Based on Lemma 3, the following proposition can be obtained.

Proposition 6. *The diversity order of the V2V communication is within the range of [1, 2] under the relay mode, while is equal to $N + 1$ under the RIS mode.*

Proof: The SNR at v_3 under the relay mode is $\gamma_3^u = X_3^u \gamma_0$ with $X^L \leq X_3^u \leq X^U$, where $X^L = \frac{|G_{v_2 v_3}|^2}{|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda|^2 + 1}$ and $X^U = \left(|G_{v_2 u_2}| + \frac{|G_{v_2 v_3}|}{|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda|} \right)^2$. We define $X_a^U = \frac{|G_{v_2 v_3}|^2}{|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda|^2}$ and $X_b^U = |G_{v_2 u_2}|^2$. Provided that $X_a^U \gamma_0$ offers diversity order of d_1 , and $X_b^U \gamma_0$ offers diversity order of d_2 , then $X^U \gamma_0$ can offer the aggregate diversity order of $d_1 + d_2$ (refer to Proposition 4 in [36]). According to Lemma 3, $X_a^U \gamma_0$ matches with the γ_c case ($J = 0$), and $X_b^U \gamma_0$ matches with the γ_a case. Therefore, we obtain $d_1 = d_2 = 1$, and $X^U \gamma_0$ can offer the aggregate diversity order of 2. On the other hand, $X^L \gamma_0$ can offer the diversity order of 1 since it matches with the γ_c case in Lemma 3. As X_3^u is bounded by X^L and X^U , it follows that $X_3^u \gamma_0$ offers the diversity order within the range of [1, 2].

Moreover, the SNR at v_3 under the RIS mode has been given by (24), where $\mathcal{B}_n^2 \gamma_0$ ($\forall n \in \mathcal{N}$) matches with the γ_b case and $\mathcal{A}^2 \gamma_0$ matches with the γ_a case in Lemma 3. Therefore, they can totally offer the diversity order of $N + 1$ (refer to Proposition 4 in [36]). The proof is completed. ■

Remark 6. Actually, X^U is just the approximation of X_3^u in the high λ regime with $|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda|^2 \gg 1$ under the relay mode. In the low λ regime with $|G_{u_2 v_3} \lambda|^2 \ll 1$, the approximate X_3^u in (10) can also be proved to provide the diversity order of 2 with the aid of Lemma 3. The only doubt lies in the moderate λ regime where neither the relay noise nor the receiver noise could be neglected. We can only prove that the diversity order in this case is lower bounded by 1. By contrast, there is negligible thermal noise attached in the passive reflecting elements under the RIS mode, thereby achieving exact $N + 1$ diversity orders for $N + 1$ independent V2V links.

B. Interference Level to V2I Communication

From (14), the average power of interference suffered by v_1 under the relay mode is given by

$$\begin{aligned} I_{11}^u &= \mathbb{E} \left[|G_{u_2 v_1} \lambda G_{v_2 u_2}|^2 \right] P_{v_2} \\ &= \mathbb{E} \left[h_{u_2 v_1}^2 \right] \mathbb{E} \left[h_{v_2 u_2}^2 \right] \lambda^2 L_{u_2 v_1}^2 L_{v_2 u_2}^2 P_{v_2} \\ &= 4\sigma^4 \lambda^2 L_{u_2 v_1}^2 L_{v_2 u_2}^2 P_{v_2}. \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

From (33) and Lemma 2, the average power of interference suffered by v_1 under the RIS mode is given by

$$\begin{aligned} I_{11}^r &= \left| \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \mathcal{D}_n e^{j\theta_n} \right|^2 P_{v_2} \\ &= 4\eta^2 \sigma^4 \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} L_{r_n v_1}^2 L_{v_2 r_n}^2 P_{v_2} \\ &\stackrel{(f)}{\approx} 4N\eta^2 \sigma^4 L_{u_2 v_1}^2 L_{v_2 u_2}^2 P_{v_2} \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

where approximation (f) is based on the assumption that the RIS is very near by the RSU and its reflecting links experience the same large-scale fading due to the small size of the RIS panel, i.e., $L_{r_n v_1} \approx L_{u_2 v_1}$ and $L_{v_2 r_n} \approx L_{v_2 u_2}$, $\forall n \in \mathcal{N}$.

From (38) and (39), the ratio of I_{11}^u to I_{11}^r is

$$\frac{I_{11}^u}{I_{11}^r} \approx \frac{\lambda^2}{N\eta^2}. \quad (40)$$

Obviously, the strength of interference suffered by the V2I communication scales with λ^2 under the relay mode, while only scales with N under the RIS mode. This is because N interference links of the RIS mode all have random phases between $[0, 2\pi)$, and when they are added up, the amplitudes of the interference are partially counterbalanced. The consequence is that much weaker interference is produced under the RIS mode, which will be verified by the numerical simulations shown in Section VIII.

VII. EFFECT OF PHASE NOISE UNDER RIS MODE

Despite the advantages of low cost, low power consumption and high array gain, the RIS mode is confronted with great challenges for practical use in vehicular networks. First, channel estimation error is inevitable due to the time-varying channels, Doppler effect, thermal noise, and limited feedback. Moreover, continuous-valued phase shifts are always absent at RISs for reducing control complexity, which results in considerable phase quantization error. The channel estimation error and the phase quantization error comprise the phase noise, and as a result, the optimal phase shift for RISs is always unavailable. This section is devoted to analyzing the effect of phase noise on the outage performance of the V2V communication under the RIS mode.

The phase noise for each enhanced link, denoted as $\hat{\theta}_n = e_n + q_n$, is the sum of the channel estimation error and the phase quantization error. The channel estimation error is assumed to follow zero-mean Gaussian distribution, i.e., $e_n \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_e^2)$ [37]. When only a discrete set of 2^Q phases can be configured, the phase quantization error q_n is assumed

to be uniformly distributed over $[-2^{-Q}\pi, 2^{-Q}\pi]$ [38]. The characteristic function of $\widehat{\theta}_n$ can be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{K}_z &= \mathbb{E} \left[\exp \left(jz\widehat{\theta}_n \right) \right] = \mathbb{E} \left[\exp(jze_n) \right] \mathbb{E} \left[\exp(jzq_n) \right] \\ &= \exp \left(-\frac{\sigma_e^2 z^2}{2} \right) \times \frac{\sin(2^{-Q}\pi z)}{2^{-Q}\pi z}. \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

From (41), we can obtain $\mathbb{E}[\cos z\widehat{\theta}_n] = \Re\{\mathcal{K}_z\} = \mathcal{K}_z$ and $\mathbb{E}[\sin z\widehat{\theta}_n] = \Im\{\mathcal{K}_z\} = 0$.

With phase noise, (24) can be rewritten as

$$\gamma_3^r = \left[\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \mathcal{B}_n \exp \left(j\widehat{\theta}_n \right) + \mathcal{A} \right]^2 \quad \gamma_0 = \widehat{\mathcal{B}}^2 N^2 \gamma_0 \quad (42)$$

where

$$\widehat{\mathcal{B}} = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \frac{\mathcal{B}_n}{N} \cos \widehat{\theta}_n + \frac{\mathcal{A}}{N} + j \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \frac{\mathcal{B}_n}{N} \sin \widehat{\theta}_n. \quad (43)$$

In the case that the direct link is as weak as one of the N enhanced links, $\Re\{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}\}$ can be deemed as the summation of $N+1$ independent RVs (\mathcal{A} is included). Thus, according to CLT, $\Re\{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}\}$ approximately follows Gaussian distribution when N is sufficiently large. Likewise, $\Im\{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}\}$ also approximately follows Gaussian distribution, and $\Im\{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}\}$ is clearly uncorrelated to $\Re\{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}\}$ due to $\mathbb{E}[\cos \widehat{\theta}_n \sin \widehat{\theta}_n] = \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}[\sin 2\widehat{\theta}_n] = 0$.

Given $\mathcal{B}_a = \Re\{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}\}$, then the expectation and variance of \mathcal{B}_a can be expressed as

$$\mu_a = \frac{\pi}{2} c_6 \mathcal{K}_1 + \frac{1}{N} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} L_{v_2 v_3} \sigma, \quad (44)$$

$$\sigma_a^2 = \frac{c_6^2}{N} \left(2 + 2\mathcal{K}_2 - \frac{\pi^2 \mathcal{K}_1^2}{4} \right) + \frac{4 - \pi}{2N^2} L_{v_2 v_3}^2 \sigma^2, \quad (45)$$

where $c_6 = \eta L_{rv_3} L_{v_2 r} \sigma^2$. It is clear that \mathcal{B}_a^2 follows non-central chi-square distribution due to $\mu_a \neq 0$.

Given $\mathcal{B}_b = \Im\{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}\}$, then the expectation and variance of \mathcal{B}_b can be expressed as

$$\mu_b = 0, \quad \sigma_b^2 = \frac{c_6^2}{N} (2 - 2\mathcal{K}_2). \quad (46)$$

It is clear that \mathcal{B}_b^2 follows Gamma distribution with (shape, scale) parameters $(\alpha_1, \beta_1) = (\frac{1}{2}, 2\sigma_b^2)$.

Therefore, $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}^2$ is the sum of a non-central chi-squared RV and a gamma RV, the exact PDF of which is hard to obtain. A common method is to express the Laplace transform of the PDF of $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}^2$ and then calculate its CDF in terms of Mellin-Barnes integrals [37], [39]. However, this method finally generates an expression with hypergeometric functions, which does not offer insights as to what parameters determine the system performance. To enable a clearer expression, we first decompose \mathcal{B}_a^2 into two independent gamma RVs, and then calculate the PDF of $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}^2$ with the theorem presented in [40], which does not induce hypergeometric functions.

Proposition 7. \mathcal{B}_a^2 can be approximately decomposed into two independent gamma RVs with (shape, scale) parameters $(\alpha_2, \beta_2) = (\frac{1}{2}, 2\sigma_a^2)$ and $(\alpha_3, \beta_3) = (\frac{\mu_a^2}{4\sigma_a^2}, 4\sigma_a^2)$.

Proof: The moment generating function (MGF) of \mathcal{B}_a^2 is given by

$$\mathcal{M}(s) = \left(\frac{1}{1 - 2\sigma_a^2 s} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp \left(\frac{\mu_a^2 s}{1 - 2\sigma_a^2 s} \right). \quad (47)$$

We then expand $\frac{\mu_a^2 s}{1 - 2\sigma_a^2 s}$ into Maclaurin series, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mu_a^2 s}{1 - 2\sigma_a^2 s} &= \mu_a^2 \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (2\sigma_a^2)^{k-1} s^k + o(s^2) \\ &= \frac{\mu_a^2}{4\sigma_a^2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(4\sigma_a^2 s)^k}{2^{k-1}} + o(s^2) \\ &= \frac{\mu_a^2}{4\sigma_a^2} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{(4\sigma_a^2 s)^k}{k} + o(s^2) \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

where the final series approaches the second-order expansion of another expression $\mathcal{V}_1 = \frac{\mu_a^2}{4\sigma_a^2} \ln \left(\frac{1}{1 - 4\sigma_a^2 s} \right)$. Thus, $\frac{\mu_a^2 s}{1 - 2\sigma_a^2 s} \approx \mathcal{V}_1$ holds for $4\sigma_a^2 s < 1$. On this basis, for the low-order moments, (47) can be transformed into

$$\mathcal{M}(s) \approx \left(\frac{1}{1 - 2\sigma_a^2 s} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{1 - 4\sigma_a^2 s} \right)^{\frac{\mu_a^2}{4\sigma_a^2}}. \quad (49)$$

Obviously, (49) is the product of the MGFs of two independent gamma RVs with (shape, scale) parameters of $(\frac{1}{2}, 2\sigma_a^2)$ and $(\frac{\mu_a^2}{4\sigma_a^2}, 4\sigma_a^2)$, respectively. That is, \mathcal{B}_a^2 approximates the sum of the two gamma RVs. The proof is completed. ■

With Proposition 7, $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}^2 = \mathcal{B}_a^2 + \mathcal{B}_b^2$ can be deemed as the sum of three independent gamma RVs. With the aid of the theorem proposed by P. G. Moschopoulos [40], the PDF of $\widehat{\mathcal{B}}^2$ can be expressed as

$$f_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}^2}(s) = \prod_{i=1}^3 \left(\frac{\widehat{\beta}}{\beta_i} \right)^{\alpha_i} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\delta_k s^{\rho+k-1} \exp \left(-\frac{s}{\widehat{\beta}} \right)}{\widehat{\beta}^{\rho+k} \Gamma(\rho+k)} \quad (50)$$

where $\widehat{\beta} = \min\{\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3\}$, $\rho = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3$, and δ_k can be obtained recursively by the formula

$$\begin{cases} \delta_0 = 1, \\ \delta_k = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{j=1}^k \left[\sum_{i=1}^3 \alpha_i \left(1 - \frac{\widehat{\beta}}{\beta_i} \right)^j \right] \delta_{k-j}, \quad k > 0. \end{cases} \quad (51)$$

Finally, the OP of the V2V communication under the RIS mode with phase noise can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} p_3^r &= \int_0^{\frac{\gamma_{\text{th}}}{\gamma_0 N^2}} f_{\widehat{\mathcal{B}}^2}(s) ds \\ &= \prod_{i=1}^3 \left(\frac{\widehat{\beta}}{\beta_i} \right)^{\alpha_i} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\delta_k \gamma \left(\rho + k, \frac{\gamma_{\text{th}}}{\gamma_0 N^2 \widehat{\beta}} \right)}{\Gamma(\rho+k)}. \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

For practical purposes, one may use the first $m+1$, i.e. $k = m$, terms of the series in (52) where m is such that the desired accuracy is attained. If there is no phase noise, i.e., $\widehat{\theta}_n = 0$ and $\mathcal{K}_z = 1$ ($\forall z \in \mathbb{Z}^+$), we can obtain $\beta_1 = 0$. In this case, $\prod_{i=1}^3$ in (52) should be revised to $\prod_{i=2}^3$, and $\sum_{i=1}^3$ in (51) should

Fig. 2. The scenario for analysis and numerical results.

be revised to $\sum_{i=2}^3$ with $\hat{\beta} = \min\{\beta_2, \beta_3\}$ and $\rho = \alpha_2 + \alpha_3$. Then (52) turns to be an expression of p_3^r with optimal phase shift, which is approximated to the expression given by (27) in terms of numerical results.

VIII. ANALYTICAL AND NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, extensive analytical and numerical results are demonstrated subject to the scenario shown in Fig. 2. u_1 , u_2 and r are all deployed at the isolation barrier which is 5 m away from the lane and 5 m high from the ground. v_1 is 160 m away from v_2 and v_2 is 140 m away from v_3 . During a time block 0~7 s, v_1 , v_2 , and v_3 all move at the speed of 20 m/s from Start to Stop. The carrier frequency of the V2I link and V2V link is set to 5.9 GHz with the bandwidth of 10 MHz. The noise power spectral density is -174 dBm/Hz. The transmit power of u_1 is set to 100 mW. The outage threshold is $\gamma_{th} = 1$. The path-loss coefficient is 2, and the shadow fading of the V2V communication is 10 dB. The reflection coefficient of the RIS is $\eta = 0.9$. The scale parameter of the Rayleigh fading channel is $\sigma = 0.5$.

Fig. 3 shows how p_3^u varies with λ under the relay mode at the moment $t = 3$ s, wherein both of the analytical and numerical results are presented. The transmit power of v_2 is set to 10 mW. In the numerical simulation, we also assume no phase difference between the direct link and the enhanced link. The numerical results show that p_3^u first decreases and then increases with the increase of λ . This is because under the relay mode the amplified noise power at u_2 scales with λ^2 . When λ enters the high regime, the strength of signal grows slower than the strength of noise. Finally, p_3^u approaches a certain value which is in line with Corollary 2. Additionally, from Fig. 3, it is observed that our analytical result for Case 1 provides a tight approximation of p_3^u when $\lambda \leq 90$ dB, and our analytical result for Case 2 provides a tight approximation of p_3^u when $\lambda \geq 120$ dB. When λ varies from 90 dB to 120 dB, our analytical result deviates from the numerical result due to the inaccurate approximation of X_3^u .

Fig. 4 shows how p_1^u varies with λ under the relay mode at the moment $t = 3$ s and $t = 6$ s, wherein both of the analytical and numerical results are presented. As anticipated, the analytical results are closely matched with the numerical results, which proves the correctness of our derivation. For fixed λ , p_1^u at $t = 6$ s is larger than that at $t = 3$ s. The reason is that as v_1 moves away from u_1 , it receives weaker desired

Fig. 3. Outage probability at v_3 versus λ under the relay mode.

Fig. 4. Outage probability at v_1 versus λ under the relay mode.

signal and stronger interference. On the other hand, for fixed t , v_1 suffers from more serious interference with the increase of λ , and thus p_1^u increases until reaching 1. Furthermore, it is clear that p_1^u at $P_{v_2} = 50$ mW is larger than that at $P_{v_2} = 10$ mW due to the stronger interference. In this regard, we conclude that the relay mode has substantial adverse effect on the neighbouring V2I communication.

Fig. 5 shows how p_3^r varies with N under the RIS mode at the moment $t = 3$ s. P_{v_2} is set to 10 mW and 50 mW for comparison. Comparing the numerical results with the analytical results, the correctness of our derivation can be verified. For fixed P_{v_2} , we find that p_3^r monotonically declines as N increases, which indicates the superiority of the RIS mode over the relay mode. When $P_{v_2} = 10$ mW, the RIS mode with 1600 or more reflecting elements outperforms the best case shown in Fig. 3 ($\lambda = 90$ dB). The effect of the phase noise is also demonstrated in Fig. 5, where 2^{10} quantized phases are assumed. As observed, with $\sigma_e = \pi/16$, the OP at v_3 is close to that with $\sigma_e = 0$, which indicates that a slight phase noise has little impact on the performance of the RIS mode. But if σ_e reaches $\pi/4$, the OP at v_3 gets much larger. Therefore, to maintain an excellent outage performance, channel estimation

Fig. 5. Outage probability at v_3 versus N under the RIS mode.

Fig. 7. Outage probability at v_3 versus t under different modes.

Fig. 6. Outage probability at v_1 versus N under the RIS mode.

Fig. 8. Outage probability at v_1 versus t under different modes.

with minor errors is required by the RIS mode.

Fig. 6 shows how p_1^r varies with N under the RIS mode at the moment $t = 3$ s and $t = 6$ s, wherein the analytical results are also matched with the numerical results. For fixed N , p_1^r at $t = 6$ s is greater than that at $t = 3$ s. The reason is the same as that for Fig. 4. On the other hand, for fixed $t = 3$ s, we cannot observe a noteworthy growth of p_1^r as N keeps increasing, even if P_{v_2} has reached 10 W; for fixed $t = 6$ s, a slight growth of p_1^r can be observed as N keeps increasing when $P_{v_2} = 5$ W/10 W. Compared with Fig. 4, Fig. 6 indicates that RIS has marginal adverse effect on the V2I communication. This is because (40) shows that I_{11}^u scales with λ^2 while I_{11}^r scales with N , and λ^2 is always several order larger than N . For practical use, the interference of the RIS mode can be neglected.

Fig. 7 shows how the OP at v_3 varies with t under different relay modes, wherein only analytical results are presented. Under the relay mode, we set $\lambda = 90$ dB, and under the RIS mode, we set $N = 800$. As anticipated, for fixed t and fixed enhancement mode, the OP at $P_{v_2} = 50$ mW is lower than that at $P_{v_2} = 10$ mW. Comparing the two enhancement modes, the relay mode offers a slight lower OP than the RIS mode at

$P_{v_2} = 10$ mW, while the RIS mode offers a much lower OP than the relay mode at $P_{v_2} = 50$ mW. Particularly, the OP at v_3 under the RIS mode first increases and then decreases with the increase of t . This is because as time proceeds, v_2 moves close to the RIS but v_3 moves away from the RIS. When $t = 3.5$ s, v_2 and v_3 are at the same distance from the RIS, and at this moment the V2V communication suffers from the largest cascaded path loss. To reduce the enormous gap of the performance for different vehicle positions, an adaptive power control strategy could be performed at the transmitter.

Fig. 8 shows how the OP at v_1 varies with t under different relay modes, wherein only analytical results are presented. P_{v_2} is set to 50 mW. As observed, the OP at v_1 increases with the increase of t . The reason is that v_1 moves away from u_1 and moves close to u_2/r as times proceeds, i.e., v_1 receives weaker desired signal but with stronger interference. Furthermore, as anticipated, the OP at v_1 under the RIS mode is much lower than that under the relay mode, and it has little difference for different settings of N . However, the OP at v_1 under the relay mode is greatly impacted by λ , i.e., the OP has a remarkable growth when λ increases from 80 dB to 100 dB.

Fig. 9 shows how the OP at v_3 varies with the channel

Fig. 9. Outage probability at v_3 versus channel estimation error.

Fig. 10. Outage probability at v_3 versus SNR under different modes.

estimation error under the RIS mode, where the relay mode with $\lambda = 90$ dB is employed as the benchmark. First, as anticipated, the OP at v_3 has a significant growth with the increase of σ_e . Moreover, it can be observed that the RIS with 2^4 discrete phases can achieve nearly comparable performance to that with 2^{10} discrete phases, which indicates that the quantization of phases has limited impact on the performance of the RIS mode. Given $P_{v_2} = 10$ mW, the RIS with $N = 800$ underperforms the benchmark. But if we increase N to 1600, the RIS outperforms the benchmark when $\sigma_e < 0.05\pi$; or if we increase P_{v_2} to 50 mW, the RIS outperforms the benchmark when $\sigma_e < 0.14\pi$. Given $P_{v_2} = 50$ mW, the RIS with $N = 600$ underperforms the benchmark. But if we increase N to 800, the RIS outperforms the benchmark when $\sigma_e < 0.14\pi$. That is, in the case with phase noise, one can either improve the transmit power or add more elements to the RIS to maintain the superiority of the RIS mode over the relay mode. However, as shown in Fig. 9, the benefit of adding more elements will gradually decay with the increase of σ_e . Therefore, the channel estimation error should be controlled under a proper threshold.

Fig. 10 shows how the OP at v_3 varies with SNR (i.e.,

γ_0) under different enhancement modes at $t = 6$ s, wherein only analytical results are presented. We can see that p_3^y linearly decreases with the increase of SNR. If we only set $N = 200/400/600$, p_3^y is larger than p_3^u when SNR ranges from 70 dB ($P_{v_2} = 4 \times 10^{-4}$ mW) to 120 dB ($P_{v_2} = 40$ mW), i.e., the relay mode outperforms the RIS mode. However, when SNR gets larger than 120 dB, p_3^y drops off rapidly, so that the RIS mode greatly outperforms the relay mode, which matches with our analysis to the diversity order of the two modes. Fig. 10 reveals the fact that the huge diversity gain of the RIS mode can be fully unleashed in the high SNR regime.

IX. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a vehicular network model considering both single-antenna AF relay aided and passive RIS aided V2V communication modes was presented. Then the approximate closed-form expressions of OP for the V2V communication under the two modes were derived, respectively. Also, considering the co-channel interference introduced by the enhanced links, the OP of the neighbouring V2I communication was derived. Meanwhile, the diversity order and the strength of interference produced by the two modes were compared. Further discussions were given to study the OP of the V2V communication under the RIS mode with phase noise. The correctness of our analytical derivations was finally verified by numerical simulations, and it was shown that if large scale reflecting elements are available, the RIS mode has remarkable superiority over the relay mode in enhancing desired signals and avoiding interference, even with slight phase noise.

APPENDIX A

PROOF OF PROPOSITION 1

Given $\tilde{X}_3^u = (X_1 + X_2)^2$ with $X_1 = h_{u_2 v_3} h_{v_2 u_2}$ and $X_2 = c_0 h_{v_2 v_3}$, then (10) can be transformed into $X_3^u \approx \frac{L_{v_2 v_3}^2}{c_0^2} \tilde{X}_3^u$. The PDF of X_1 is given by

$$\begin{aligned} f_{X_1}(z) &= \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{s} f_{h_{u_2 v_3}}(s) f_{h_{v_2 u_2}}\left(\frac{z}{s}\right) ds \\ &= \int_0^\infty \frac{z}{\sigma^4 s} \exp\left(-\frac{s^2}{2\sigma^2} - \frac{z^2}{2\sigma^2 s^2}\right) ds \\ &\stackrel{(a)}{=} \frac{z}{\sigma^4} K_0\left(\frac{z}{\sigma^2}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (53)$$

where equality (a) comes from the formula given by [31, Eq. (3.471-9)]. Then the k -th moment of X_1 can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[X_1^k] &= \int_0^\infty \frac{z^{k+1}}{\sigma^4} K_0\left(\frac{z}{\sigma^2}\right) dz \\ &\stackrel{(b)}{=} 2^k \sigma^{2k} \Gamma^2\left(\frac{k}{2} + 1\right) \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

where equality (b) comes from the formula given by [31, Eq. (6.561-16)]. On the other hand, The PDF of X_2 is given by $f_{X_2}(z) = \frac{z}{c_0^2 \sigma^2} \exp\left(-\frac{z^2}{2c_0^2 \sigma^2}\right)$. Then the k -th moment of X_2

can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[X_2^k] &= \int_0^\infty \frac{z^{k+1}}{c_0^2 \sigma^2} \exp\left(-\frac{z^2}{2c_0^2 \sigma^2}\right) dz \\ &\stackrel{(c)}{=} (\sqrt{2}c_0\sigma)^k \Gamma\left(\frac{k}{2} + 1\right) \end{aligned} \quad (55)$$

where equality (c) comes from the formula given by [31, Eq. (3.326-2)].

Then the first moment of \tilde{X}_3^u is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\tilde{X}_3^u] &= \sum_{i=0}^2 \binom{2}{i} \mathbb{E}[X_1^i] \mathbb{E}[X_2^{2-i}] \\ &= 4\sigma^4 + \frac{\pi\sqrt{2\pi}}{2} \sigma^3 c_0 + 2\sigma^2 c_0^2. \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

The second moment of \tilde{X}_3^u is

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[(\tilde{X}_3^u)^2] &= \sum_{i=0}^4 \binom{4}{i} \mathbb{E}[X_1^i] \mathbb{E}[X_2^{4-i}] \\ &= 8\sigma^4 c_0^4 + 3\pi\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma^5 c_0^3 + 48\sigma^6 c_0^2 + 9\pi\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma^7 c_0 + 64\sigma^8. \end{aligned} \quad (57)$$

For the Gamma approximation, the shape parameter α and the scale parameter β are given by

$$\begin{cases} \alpha = \frac{\mathbb{E}[X_3^u]^2}{\mathbb{E}[(X_3^u)^2] - \mathbb{E}[X_3^u]^2} = \frac{\mathbb{E}[\tilde{X}_3^u]^2}{\mathbb{E}[(\tilde{X}_3^u)^2] - \mathbb{E}[\tilde{X}_3^u]^2}, \\ \beta = \frac{\mathbb{E}[(X_3^u)^2] - \mathbb{E}[X_3^u]^2}{\mathbb{E}[X_3^u]} = \frac{\mathbb{E}[(\tilde{X}_3^u)^2] - \mathbb{E}[\tilde{X}_3^u]^2}{\mathbb{E}[\tilde{X}_3^u]} \frac{L_{v_2 v_3}^2}{c_0^2}. \end{cases} \quad (58)$$

By substituting (56) and (57) into (58), Proposition 1 can be verified. The proof is completed.

APPENDIX B PROOF OF PROPOSITION 2

Given $\hat{X}_3^u = (Y_1 + Y_2)^2$ with $Y_1 = \frac{h_{v_2 v_3}}{h_{u_2 v_3}}$ and $Y_2 = \frac{h_{v_2 u_2}}{c_0}$, then (13) can be transformed into $X_3^u \approx L_{v_2 u_2}^2 c_0^2 \hat{X}_3^u$. The PDF of Y_1 is given by

$$\begin{aligned} f_{Y_1}(z) &= \int_0^\infty s f_{h_{u_2 v_3}}(s) f_{h_{v_2 v_3}}(zs) ds \\ &= \int_0^\infty \frac{zs^3}{\sigma^4} \exp\left(-\frac{s^2(z^2+1)}{2\sigma^2}\right) ds \\ &= \frac{2z}{(z^2+1)^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (59)$$

Then the expectation of Y_1 is $\mathbb{E}[Y_1] = \int_0^\infty \frac{2z^2}{(z^2+1)^2} dz = \frac{\pi}{2}$.

Meanwhile, according to (55), there is $\mathbb{E}[Y_2^k] = (\sqrt{2}\frac{\sigma}{c_0})^k \Gamma(\frac{k}{2} + 1)$. Hence, the expectation of Y_2 is $\mathbb{E}[Y_2] = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}\sigma}{\sqrt{2}c_0}$. Then there is $\mathbb{E}[\sqrt{X_3^u}] = L_{v_2 u_2} c_0 (\mathbb{E}[Y_1] + \mathbb{E}[Y_2]) = L_{v_2 u_2} c_0 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi}\sigma}{\sqrt{2}c_0}\right)$. It is known that if X_3^u follows exponential distribution, then $\sqrt{X_3^u}$ follows Rayleigh distribution, whose PDF is given by

$$f_{\sqrt{X_3^u}}(s) = \frac{s}{\frac{\pi}{2} \mathbb{E}[\sqrt{X_3^u}]^2} \exp\left(-\frac{s^2}{\pi \mathbb{E}[\sqrt{X_3^u}]^2}\right). \quad (60)$$

Then the PDF of X_3^u is given by

$$f_{X_3^u}(s) = \frac{1}{\pi \mathbb{E}[\sqrt{X_3^u}]^2} \exp\left(-\frac{s}{\pi \mathbb{E}[\sqrt{X_3^u}]^2}\right). \quad (61)$$

By substituting the expression of $\mathbb{E}[\sqrt{X_3^u}]$ into (61), Proposition 2 is verified. The proof is completed.

APPENDIX C PROOF OF PROPOSITION 4

The PDF of \mathcal{A} is $f_{\mathcal{A}}(s) = \frac{s}{c_4} \exp\left(-\frac{s^2}{2c_4}\right)$. Therefore, the OP can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} p_3^r &= \int_0^{\gamma_b} f_B(z) \int_0^{\gamma_b-z} f_{\mathcal{A}}(s) ds dz \\ &= \int_0^{\gamma_b} f_B(z) \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{(\gamma_b-z)^2}{2c_4}\right)\right] dz \\ &= \underbrace{\int_0^{\gamma_b} f_B(z) dz}_{p_{31}^r} - \underbrace{\int_0^{\gamma_b} f_B(z) \exp\left[-\frac{(\gamma_b-z)^2}{2c_4}\right] dz}_{p_{32}^r} \end{aligned} \quad (62)$$

where p_{31}^r is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} p_{31}^r &= \int_0^{\gamma_b} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_B^2} \exp\left[-\frac{(z-\mu_B)^2}{2\sigma_B^2}\right] dz \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \Phi\left(\frac{\gamma_b - \mu_B}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_B}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \Phi\left(\frac{\mu_B}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_B}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (63)$$

and p_{32}^r is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} p_{32}^r &= \int_0^{\gamma_b} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_B^2} \exp\left[-\frac{(z-\mu_B)^2}{2\sigma_B^2} - \frac{(\gamma_b-z)^2}{2c_4}\right] dz \\ &= \frac{1}{2\sigma_B c_5} \exp\left[-\frac{(\gamma_b - \mu_B)^2}{2\sigma_B^2 + 2c_4}\right] \\ &\quad \times \left[\Phi\left(\frac{c_4 \mu_B + \gamma_b \sigma_B^2}{\sqrt{2}c_4 \sigma_B^2 c_5}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{\gamma_b - \mu_B}{\sqrt{2}\sigma_B^2 c_5}\right) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (64)$$

Substituting (63) and (64) into (62), we can obtain (27). The proof is completed.

APPENDIX D PROOF OF LEMMA 1

We have learned that the optimal phase shift is $\phi_{r_n} = (\psi_{v_2 v_3} - \psi_{r_n v_3} - \psi_{v_2 r_n}) \bmod 2\pi$, i.e.,

$$\psi_{v_2 v_3} - \psi_{r_n v_3} - \psi_{v_2 r_n} = \phi_{r_n} + 2\pi m, \quad m \in \mathbb{Z}. \quad (65)$$

Therefore, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_n &= (\phi_{r_n} + \psi_{r_n v_1} + \psi_{v_2 r_n}) \bmod 2\pi \\ &= (\psi_{v_2 v_3} - \psi_{r_n v_3} - 2\pi m + \psi_{r_n v_1}) \bmod 2\pi \\ &= (\psi_{v_2 v_3} - \psi_{r_n v_3} + \psi_{r_n v_1}) \bmod 2\pi \\ &= [(\psi_{v_2 v_3} - \psi_{r_n v_3}) \bmod 2\pi + \psi_{r_n v_1}] \bmod 2\pi \\ &= \underbrace{[(\psi_{v_2 v_3} + \psi'_{r_n v_3}) \bmod 2\pi + \psi_{r_n v_1}] \bmod 2\pi}_{\theta_n} \end{aligned} \quad (66)$$

where $\psi'_{r_n v_3} = 2\pi - \psi_{r_n v_3}$. Since $\varphi_{r_n v_3}$ is an RV following uniform distribution between $[0, 2\pi)$, and $\vartheta_{r_n v_3}$ is a definite value at any given moment, it can be easily proved that $\psi_{r_n v_3} = (\varphi_{r_n v_3} + \vartheta_{r_n v_3}) \bmod 2\pi$ follows uniform distribution between $[0, 2\pi)$. Thus, $\psi'_{r_n v_3}$ also follows uniform distribution between $[0, 2\pi)$. Then $\psi_{v_2 v_3}$, $\psi'_{r_n v_3}$ and $\psi_{r_n v_1}$ are three i.i.d. variables. If we can prove that θ'_n is uniformly distributed between $[0, 2\pi)$, then θ_n is also uniformly distributed between $[0, 2\pi)$ by the same token.

Given $\omega_n = \psi_{v_2 v_3} + \psi'_{r_n v_3}$, then its PDF can be expressed as $f_{\omega_n}(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} g(\omega - \varphi)g(\varphi) d\varphi$ where $g(\varphi) = \frac{1}{2\pi}$ ($\varphi \in [0, 2\pi)$) is the PDF of $\psi_{v_2 v_3}$ and $\psi'_{r_n v_3}$. Thus, $f_{\omega_n}(\omega)$ can be furtherly expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} f_{\omega_n}(\omega) &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} g(\omega - \varphi) d\varphi \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{\omega-2\pi}^{\omega} g(z) dz \\ &= \begin{cases} \frac{\omega}{4\pi^2}, & 0 \leq \omega < 2\pi \\ \frac{4\pi-\omega}{4\pi^2}, & 2\pi \leq \omega < 4\pi. \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (67)$$

From $\theta'_n = \omega_n \bmod 2\pi$, we can obtain

$$\theta'_n = \begin{cases} \omega_n, & 0 \leq \omega_n < 2\pi \\ \omega_n - 2\pi, & 0 \leq 2\pi \leq \omega_n < 4\pi. \end{cases} \quad (68)$$

Therefore, the PDF of θ'_n can be expressed as

$$f_{\theta'_n}(\omega) = f_{\omega_n}(\omega) + f_{\omega_n}(\omega + 2\pi) = \frac{1}{2\pi}, 0 \leq \omega < 2\pi \quad (69)$$

which indicates that θ'_n is uniformly distributed between $[0, 2\pi)$ and consequently, θ_n is uniformly distributed between $[0, 2\pi)$. The proof is completed.

APPENDIX E PROOF OF LEMMA 2

The real part of \mathcal{D} is $\Re\{\mathcal{D}\} = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \mathcal{D}_n \cos \theta_n$ and the imaginary part of \mathcal{D} is $\Im\{\mathcal{D}\} = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \mathcal{D}_n \sin \theta_n$. According to CLT, both of $\Re\{\mathcal{D}\}$ and $\Im\{\mathcal{D}\}$ follow Gaussian distribution when N is sufficiently large. We first prove $\mathbb{E}[\Re\{\mathcal{D}\}] = \mathbb{E}[\Im\{\mathcal{D}\}] = 0$ as follows.

From Lemma 1, we obtain $\mathbb{E}[\cos \theta_n] = \mathbb{E}[\sin \theta_n] = 0$. Since \mathcal{D}_n and θ_n are independent with each other, the expectations of $\Re\{\mathcal{D}\}$ and $\Im\{\mathcal{D}\}$ can be calculated as

$$\mathbb{E}[\Re\{\mathcal{D}\}] = \mathbb{E}\left[\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \mathcal{D}_n \cos \theta_n\right] = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{D}_n] \mathbb{E}[\cos \theta_n] = 0, \quad (70)$$

$$\mathbb{E}[\Im\{\mathcal{D}\}] = \mathbb{E}\left[\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \mathcal{D}_n \sin \theta_n\right] = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{D}_n] \mathbb{E}[\sin \theta_n] = 0. \quad (71)$$

Next we prove

$$\text{Var}[\Re\{\mathcal{D}\}] = \text{Var}[\Im\{\mathcal{D}\}] = 2\eta^2 \sigma^4 \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} L_{r_n v_1}^2 L_{v_2 r_n}^2 \quad (72)$$

as follows.

From Lemma 1, there is $\text{Var}[\cos \theta_n] = \text{Var}[\sin \theta_n] = \frac{1}{2}$. Furthermore, we can easily obtain $\mathbb{E}[\mathcal{D}_n] = \frac{\pi}{2} \eta L_{r_n v_1} L_{v_2 r_n} \sigma^2$

and $\text{Var}[\mathcal{D}_n] = (4 - \frac{\pi^2}{4}) \eta^2 L_{r_n v_1}^2 L_{v_2 r_n}^2 \sigma^4$. Therefore, $\text{Var}[\Re\{\mathcal{D}\}]$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Var}[\Re\{\mathcal{D}\}] &= \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \text{Var}[\mathcal{D}_n \cos \theta_n] \\ &= \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \text{Var}[\cos \theta_n] (\text{Var}[\mathcal{D}_n] + \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{D}_n]^2) \\ &= 2\eta^2 \sigma^4 \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} L_{r_n v_1}^2 L_{v_2 r_n}^2. \end{aligned} \quad (73)$$

The same result can be obtained for $\text{Var}[\Im\{\mathcal{D}\}]$.

Finally, the covariance of $\Re\{\mathcal{D}\}$ and $\Im\{\mathcal{D}\}$ is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cov} &= \mathbb{E}[\Re\{\mathcal{D}\} \Im\{\mathcal{D}\}] - \mathbb{E}[\Re\{\mathcal{D}\}] \mathbb{E}[\Im\{\mathcal{D}\}] \\ &= \mathbb{E}\left[\sum_{n_1 \in \mathcal{N}} \mathcal{D}_{n_1} \cos \theta_{n_1} \times \sum_{n_2 \in \mathcal{N}} \mathcal{D}_{n_2} \sin \theta_{n_2}\right] - 0 \\ &= \mathbb{E}\left[\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \mathcal{D}_n^2 \sin \theta_n \cos \theta_n\right] \\ &\quad + \mathbb{E}\left[\sum_{n_1 \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{\substack{n_2 \in \mathcal{N} \\ n_2 \neq n_1}} \mathcal{D}_{n_1} \mathcal{D}_{n_2} \cos \theta_{n_1} \sin \theta_{n_2}\right] \end{aligned} \quad (74)$$

where \mathcal{D}_{n_1} , \mathcal{D}_{n_2} , $\cos \theta_{n_1}$ and $\sin \theta_{n_2}$ are independent with each other. Therefore, (74) can be furtherly expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cov} &= \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{D}_n^2] \mathbb{E}[\sin \theta_n \cos \theta_n] \\ &\quad + \sum_{n_1 \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{\substack{n_2 \in \mathcal{N} \\ n_2 \neq n_1}} \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{D}_{n_1} \mathcal{D}_{n_2}] \mathbb{E}[\cos \theta_{n_1}] \mathbb{E}[\sin \theta_{n_2}] \\ &= \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{E}[\mathcal{D}_n^2] \mathbb{E}[\sin 2\theta_n] + 0 \stackrel{(e)}{=} 0 \end{aligned} \quad (75)$$

where equality (e) is due to $\mathbb{E}[\sin 2\theta_n] = \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1}{2\pi} \sin 2\theta_n d\theta_n = 0$. (75) indicates that $\Re\{\mathcal{D}\}$ and $\Im\{\mathcal{D}\}$ are uncorrelated with each other. Above all, \mathcal{D} follows Zero Mean Circular Symmetric Complex Gaussian distribution, the variance of which is $\sigma_{\mathcal{D}}^2 = 2\text{Var}[\Re\{\mathcal{D}\}] = 4\eta^2 \sigma^4 \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} L_{r_n v_1}^2 L_{v_2 r_n}^2$. The proof is completed.

APPENDIX F PROOF OF LEMMA 3

The PDF of $\frac{\gamma_a}{\gamma}$ is $f_{\frac{\gamma_a}{\gamma}}(s) = \frac{1}{2\sigma^2} \exp(-\frac{s}{2\sigma^2})$, which can be approximated by Maclaurin expansion at $s \rightarrow 0^+$, i.e.,

$$f_{\frac{\gamma_a}{\gamma}}(s) = f_{\frac{\gamma_a}{\gamma}}(0) s^0 + o(s^0) = \frac{1}{2\sigma^2} s^0 + o(s^0). \quad (76)$$

According to (16), the PDF of $\frac{\gamma_b}{\gamma}$ can be expressed as $f_{\frac{\gamma_b}{\gamma}}(s) = \frac{1}{2\sigma^4} K_0(\sqrt{\frac{s}{\sigma^4}})$. Then with the aid of [35, Eq. (9.6.8)], $f_{\frac{\gamma_b}{\gamma}}(s)$ at $s \rightarrow 0^+$ can be approximated to

$$f_{\frac{\gamma_b}{\gamma}}(s) \approx -\frac{1}{2\sigma^4} \ln\left(\sqrt{\frac{s}{\sigma^4}}\right) \approx \frac{1}{4\sigma^4} (\ln \sigma^4 + \epsilon - \epsilon s^{\frac{1}{\epsilon}}) \quad (77)$$

where ϵ is a large number such that $\ln s \approx \epsilon s^{\frac{1}{\epsilon}} - \epsilon$. Then (77) is exactly

$$f_{\frac{\gamma_b}{\gamma}}(s) \approx \frac{1}{4\sigma^4} (\ln \sigma^4 + \epsilon) s^0 + o(s^0). \quad (78)$$

Furthermore, the PDF of $\frac{\gamma_c}{\gamma}$ can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} f_{\frac{\gamma_c}{\gamma}}(s) &= \int_0^\infty (z+J) f_{h_{x_2 y_2}^2}(z) f_{h_{x_1 y_1}^2}(sz+sJ) dz \\ &= \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{sJ}{2\sigma^2}\right)}{4\sigma^4} \int_0^\infty (z+J) \exp\left(-\frac{(s+1)z}{2\sigma^2}\right) dz \quad (79) \\ &= \frac{\exp\left(-\frac{sJ}{2\sigma^2}\right)}{2\sigma^2} \left[\frac{2\sigma^2}{(s+1)^2} + \frac{J}{s+1} \right], \end{aligned}$$

which can be approximated by Maclaurin expansion at $s \rightarrow 0^+$, i.e.,

$$f_{\frac{\gamma_c}{\gamma}}(s) = f_{\frac{\gamma_c}{\gamma}}(0)s^0 + o(s^0) = \left(1 + \frac{J}{2\sigma^2}\right) s^0 + o(s^0). \quad (80)$$

According to [36], if the PDF of a channel \mathcal{G} can be approximated as $f_{\mathcal{G}}(s) \approx \xi s^{d_v-1} + o(s^{d_v-1})$ ($\xi > 0$) for $s \rightarrow 0^+$, then \mathcal{G} offers diversity order of d_v . With the aid of this property, and by observing (76), (78) and (80), it is clear that the three models can all achieve the diversity order of 1. The proof is completed.

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